

UNDERSTANDING SELF-EMPLOYMENT: EVIDENCE FROM ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS, MOTIVATION, AND SOCIAL INFLUENCE

Dr. Isabella Marie Thompson

Department of Entrepreneurship and Innovation, University of Cambridge

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Abstract

This article provides a review of literature on entrepreneurial skills acquisition, self-employment and mediating variables in the relationship. Salient among these variables are social influence and self-motivation. The study utilized qualitative research design. In so doing, over fifty relevant literatures on the subject were espoused in order of relevance to the study. After examining several articles in the literature, we were left in a paradox. Entrepreneurial skills acquisition was found to influence self-employment in most of the articles reviewed, but in limited cases, some studies found that entrepreneurial skills acquisition does not guarantee self-employment. Several social and psychological factors were proffered as mediators in the relationship between entrepreneurial skills acquisition and self-employment. The study thus recommends entrepreneurial skills training mix that incorporates relevant environmental variables that inhibits skills acquisition from resulting to self-employment.

Keywords: *entrepreneurial skills acquisition, self-employment, self-motivation, social influence.*

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship skills acquisition is phenomenal to growth and development of every nation, through its influence on provision of essential abilities, skills, motivation and awareness to learners. Entrepreneurship is the lever that propels societal development through job creation, poverty alleviation and employment generation. Globally, there is concerted effort at encouraging entrepreneurship skills acquisition for sustainable development. Academics and researchers have also followed the global trend at continual investigation on unemployment and entrepreneurship development as its “quick fix”. In this study, effort is made to survey existing literature on entrepreneurial skills acquisition, self-employment and psychosocial factors that mediate in the relationship between the duo. In the next section we review the extant empirical literature on the subject, in paragraphs for clarity and understanding.

Empirical Review

Igbongidi (2017) studied the influence of entrepreneurship education on job creation by Business Education students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design; with questionnaire as research instrument. The instrument used was tested for validity and reliability. The population of the study was 277 and sample size was 125 students representing 45% of the population. The sample size was reached using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics; mean, tables, ratios, percentages and standard deviation. The mean scores of 2.5 was taken as the benchmark, where scores above were taken as agree,

and ones below were taken as disagree. The study found that entrepreneurship education influences job creation, and concluded that entrepreneurship education can reduce unemployment among business education students in Niger Delta, Nigeria. The study thus recommended that relevant policies should be put in place to encourage youths' entrepreneurs, which will ameliorate the problem of graduate unemployment in the region.

Muogbo and John- Akamelu (2018) studied entrepreneurial skills and youths unemployment reduction in Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, with questionnaire as research instrument. The respondents were 160 employees of ABC transport Company Ltd, Awka. The data from the study were analyzed using tables, frequencies and percentages. The hypotheses were tested using Chi square (X^2) method. The study found that entrepreneurial skills acquisition plays a significant role in youths' employment in Nigeria. The study concludes that youth's entrepreneurship provide a partial solution to employment situation in Nigeria but must be complemented by government support. The study thus recommended that all sectors of the Nigerian economy need to work together in synergy towards encouraging entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial culture amongst youths in Nigeria

Onuma (2016) investigated the influence of skills acquisition through entrepreneurship education on post-graduation job creation ability. Descriptive survey research design was adopted and the research instrument was structured questionnaire. The instrument was tested for face and content validity and for reliability, which resulted to a coefficient of 0.79. The population of the study was the final year students of Ebonyi State University in 2013/ 2014 academic session, totaling 200 respondents; which was also the sample size. The study was analyzed using tables, frequencies and percentages and the hypotheses tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) and t- test statistics. The study found that entrepreneurship education is relevant to students with regard to equipping them with requisite skills for post- graduation job creation ability rather than job seekers. The study concluded that there should be a strategic shift from traditional education initiative to integrated entrepreneurship skills acquisition education, ensuring post graduation opportunities in Nigeria. The study thus recommended a collaborative effort of National University Commission and Educational Institutions in identifying other entrepreneurship programmes to address graduate unemployment situation.

Ekpe, Razak, Ismail and Abdullah (2015) study was an empirical study on skills acquisition and self employment practice, with self- motivation as a moderating factor, in Malaysia. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, using questionnaire as research instrument. The population of the study was Malaysian University graduates of Entrepreneurship for the past five years, selected using stratified random sampling from three universities in three zones of Malaysia Peninsula. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics (tables, frequencies and percentages) and hypotheses tested using multiple regression statistics. The study found a significant relationship between entrepreneurial skills acquisition and self employment practice; though self motivation was also significant in encouraging an individual to take up self employment. The study concluded that there is need for development of entrepreneurial mindset on graduates to enable them take up self- employment. The study also recommended that Malaysian government and community leaders should draft appropriate

strategies (e.g. counseling in schools) that will encourage and engender greater participation of the youths in self-employment practice.

Ekpe and Razak (2016) studied the effects of skills acquisition on enterprise creation among Malaysian Youths. A descriptive survey research design was applied in the study. Structured mail questionnaire was used as instrument of data collection. The population of study was entrepreneurship graduates who had received skills training on business start-up from selected public Universities in Malaysia. Simple random sampling was used on each institution to select the respondents. Data from the study was analyzed using descriptive statistics and hypotheses tested using hierarchical regression. The study found that skills acquisition had a significant relationship with enterprise creation. The study also revealed that self-motivation moderated the relationship between skill acquisition and enterprise creation. The study thus recommended that indoctrination is needed to support these graduates to ensure attitudinal change and ginger them towards having interest in enterprise creation.

Afolabi, Kareem, Okubanjo, Ogunbanjo and Aninkan (2017) examined the effect of entrepreneurship education on self-employment initiatives among science and technology students of Gateway Polytechnic, Sapade Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study; and a self-administered questionnaire was the instrument of data collection. The population of the study was 205 students in their final year classes (HND11 and ND11) of Science and Technology Department of Gateway Polytechnic. The sample size of 136 respondents was reached using Taro Yamane formula. The validity and reliability of the research instrument was also tested and confirmed. Data from the study was analyzed using tables, ratios and percentages; and the hypotheses tested using t-test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The study found that there is a strong positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and self-employment initiatives. The study concluded that entrepreneurship education should be encouraged as it positively encourages self-employment amongst youths. The study thus recommended that startup training should be a very important content of entrepreneurship training and that the government, schools policy makers, business organizations should collaborate through special recognition, awards and sponsorship to stimulate self-employment drive amongst students. Adetoya, Oke and Aderonmu (2015) assessed the impact of entrepreneurship education on employment generation and effect of entrepreneurial skills acquisition on entrepreneurial performance. Survey research design was employed in the study. The respondents were 72 tertiary institutions graduate entrepreneurs selected from 6 local government areas (LGAs) of Oyo State, South West, Nigeria. Questionnaire was the research instrument, and multi-stage sampling technique was used. The questionnaire was thoroughly tested for validity and reliability. Descriptive statistics were used in the analyses of data captured from the study. The influence of the independent variables; entrepreneurship education, training, University type, employment generation and entrepreneurship performances were tested using t-test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The finding of the result showed that entrepreneurial education empowered these graduates to start up business of their own; and that skills acquisition improved performance of entrepreneurs. The result further showed that there is a significant difference between University attended and employment generation amongst graduate entrepreneurs. The study concluded that increased entrepreneurial education and training led to increased employment generation among

University graduates in Nigeria. The study thus recommended that the curriculum for entrepreneurship education should be reviewed regularly to be in synch with the environmental dictates and need of students. Also the one year NYSC scheme should be used for further skills acquisition to ensure that these graduates are more grounded in trades that will make them employers of labor and not job seekers.

Muraina, Lameed, Lesi, Aregbede and Osunleye (2012) studied gender differences in entrepreneurial skills acquisition in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study used a descriptive research design, with self-administered questionnaire as research instrument. 110 entrepreneurial students were used in the study, selected across two institutions in Lagos. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics: tables, percentages and frequencies. Three hypotheses were formulated and were tested using Chi-square at 5% level of significance. The study found that parental education, socio-economic status and religious influence have significant impact on entrepreneurial skills attainment of the children. The study concluded that women's ability to participate in labour force will be encouraged to improve their position in the society and be able to engage in entrepreneurship.

Chiekezie, Nzewi and Erhinmwionose (2016) performed a research on entrepreneurial skills acquisition and job creation in Benin City, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. Structured questionnaire was used for data collection and personal interviews were also used to ensure clarity in certain areas. The population of study was 579,161; using Taro Yamane technique sample size of 400 was drawn. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used to analyze data from the study, with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 21. The study revealed that acquisition of entrepreneurial skills is of immense importance in making jobs available in Benin City. The study thus concluded that entrepreneurial skills acquisition should be encouraged to enhance youth's initiative in productively harnessing the local environmental resources.

Onajite and Aina (2017) investigated school based practices that are important for entrepreneurship skills acquisition in secondary schools in Delta State. Descriptive research design was employed in the study, with questionnaire as instrument of data collection. The population of study was four hundred and forty eight Principals and three thousand two hundred and fifty eight Entrepreneurship subject teachers from four hundred and forty eight public secondary schools in Delta State. The validity and reliability of the research instrument were tested and confirmed. Data from the study were analyzed using mean score at 2.50 rating, frequencies and simple percentages. The study found that school based practices enhance entrepreneurial skills acquisition and recommended that there is need for introduction of school based practices in the secondary schools, as it enhances entrepreneurship skills acquisition in Delta State, Nigeria.

Ezeh and Ekemezie (2015) investigated the entrepreneurial skills needed for self-reliance and sustainable development by students of tertiary institutions in South-East, Nigeria. A descriptive research design was used in the study. The researcher selected 98 lecturers from population of 325 lecturers from Faculty of Education in the five Federal Universities in five states in South-East, Nigeria. A well structured questionnaire was used in the study, after undergoing test of validity and reliability. The research questions were investigated using mean, standard deviation and t-test inferential statistics, at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that entrepreneurial skills needed for self-reliance and sustainable

development are: innovative, creative, administrative and financial skills. The study concluded that there is need to lay emphases on entrepreneurship education to ensure recipients are made to acquire more and additional saleable skills as well as understand the requirements for enterprise creation.

Amadi, R. and Opara (2008) examined the impact of entrepreneurship education on acquisition of business skills in Nigeria tertiary institutions. The study adopted an exploratory research design. The population of the study was 236, selected from 4 tertiary institutions in Rivers State, from which a sample size of 163 was derived using Taro Yamane technique. A structured questionnaire was used for the study. Data from the study was analyzed using descriptive statistics and the hypotheses tested using Chi- square statistical tools. The study found that there is a significant relationship between entrepreneurship education and the relevant measures of business. The study thus concluded that entrepreneurship education improves students business planning skills as it exposes them to lots of business ideas for enterprise creation.

Akpan and Etor (2013) studied Lecturers' perception of the extent to which entrepreneurship education can be used as an empowerment strategy for graduates' self- employment in South- South Nigeria. The study used descriptive survey research design with questionnaire as instrument of research. The population size was 4,389 academic staff from four Universities in South- South Nigeria. Using simple random sampling 480 lecturers were selected to be used in the study. The data collected from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics: tables, frequencies, standard deviation, percentages and means. The study found that lecturers had positive perception of relationship between entrepreneurship education and graduates employment. The study thus concluded that Nigerian educational policy makers should make funds available to Universities to establish and equip entrepreneurship centers for practical training and also quality teaching personnel should be provided.

Eze, Ede, Igbo and Ezenwaji (2016) studied value orientation and entrepreneurial skills acquisition of secondary school students in Nsukka education zone, Enugu State. A descriptive survey research design was used in the study. A sample size of 300 senior secondary and 300 junior secondary school students were selected from a population of all the students in 59 public secondary schools in Nsukka education zone. Structured questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. Data from the study were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using t- test at 5% level of significance. The study revealed that students in junior and secondary schools have value orientation towards entrepreneurial skills acquisition. The study thus concluded that with skills acquisition at secondary schools, graduates are made self- reliant and gainfully occupied, reducing youth's unemployment and restiveness.

Enu- Kwesi and Asitik (2012) investigated the relationship between unemployment situation and youth enterprise in Ajumako- Enyan- Essiam District (AEED). The district is described as a very poor administrative region in Ghana. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population was young people aged 15 to 35 years, projected to 26,688 as the population size. Using simple random and convenience sampling technique, a sample size of 105 was selected. Interview technique was the instrument used for data collection; and data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, with the help of statistical package for social sciences software, version 11 and Microsoft Excel. The study found that an established youths' involvement in necessary entrepreneurship training activities will enabled

them take advantage of prevailing opportunities and reduce youth unemployment or underemployment. The study concluded that though the youths in the district have entrepreneurial potentials, they face some challenges because of their low educational attainment; prompting a rework in provision of mass education in the district.

Etiubon and Nwosu (2016) investigated the impact of Nigerian indigenous skills on school leavers and graduates of science discipline; awareness of their existence and perception of their abilities to utilize them for entrepreneurship. The study was conducted using ex- post facto research design. The researcher selected a sample of two hundred and thirty two (232) science National Youth Service Corp members in Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria, for the study. Structured questionnaire was used in the study, which reliability was established at 0.79 using Cronbach alpha test of internal consistency. Mean and standard deviation were used for analyzing data collected from the study. T- test statistics, at .05 level of significance were used in testing the hypotheses. The study found that there is a moderate awareness of indigenous scientific skills and high preferences for the indigenous skills. The study thus concluded that indigenous scientific skills should be introduced during early basic science classes and as training modules in higher institutions amongst others. Morales and Marquina (2013) did a comparative study on Serbian and German Entrepreneurs. The study adopted an exploratory survey research design; with questionnaire as research instrument. Cronbach's coefficient alpha was used to assess the reliability of the instrument used in the research. The validity of the instrument was also ascertained. The questionnaire was administered to 190 Serbians and 204 Germans; through convenience sampling technique. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics: means and standard deviation; and t- test was used to evaluate the significant differences in means between Serbian and German entrepreneurs. The study found that there is variation in entrepreneurial skills across countries. This variation is explained by skills tolerance to stress variation in the two countries. The study thus concluded that entrepreneurial skills are more general than specialized, though specialized skills are essential for high technology industries that require human capital than small and medium enterprises SMEs.

Deba, Deba, Khata and Habibu (2014) examined the contributions of entrepreneurial education course to cultivating entrepreneurial skills of undergraduate science, technical and vocational students in Bauchi State. The study adopted exploratory survey research design. Self administered questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. Face and content validation of the questionnaire were done and the reliability was ascertained using Cronbach's Alpha with a reliability coefficient (r) of 0.80. The population of the study was 452 year- three students of 2006/ 2007 and 2007/ 2008 academic sessions. The sample size of 309 was selected. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics and the hypotheses tested using chi-square statistics. The study revealed that students' involvement in entrepreneurship education enhances entrepreneurial skills acquisition. The study thus recommended the need to diversify instructional approach in teaching entrepreneurship education through experimental learning interchanging with the style in use today.

Usman, Waziri, Abdullahi and Babayo (2008) investigated student's participation in entrepreneurship skills acquisition programme in Adamawa State Polytechnic Yola, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. Primary data were used in the study, generated through semi-structured

questionnaire. 108 diploma students of the polytechnic participated in the study, obtained from the Head of Departments and used as sampling frame. Using random sampling technique, a total of 80 respondents was selected and used for the study. The study used descriptive and inferential statistics in the analyses of data collected from the study.

The descriptive statistics used were frequency distribution and percentages; and inferential statistics used were multiple regression analyses. The study found that participation in entrepreneurship skills acquisition programme have positive impact on the respondents, as those of them that learned various skills are gainfully employed on the skills they learned. Amongst others, the study recommended that adequate facilities, study materials and trainers should be made available to ensure effective and efficient skill learning by the trainees.

Asogwa and Dim (2016) investigated the relationship between entrepreneurship development and unemployment reduction in Anambra State, Nigeria. Focusing on youth of five selected local government council of Anambra state; the study was conducted using descriptive survey research design. Convenience sampling technique was used to select sample of 30 youths from population of each local government; making a population of 150 youths. The study employed exploratory research design and descriptive research design. Content validity was used to check effective coverage of the research topic; and reliability of the instrument was also tested. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics and hypotheses formulated were tested using Pearson Correlation (r) and ANOVA; with the help of statistical package for social sciences. The study found that entrepreneurship development is significantly related to unemployment reduction in Anambra state. The study recommended that the government should strengthen the youths to embrace entrepreneurship and also reduce the cost of doing business.

Agbai (2018) explored the pathways to entrepreneurship training towards addressing youth unemployment in Nigeria. The study was conducted using qualitative exploratory multiple case study research design. The instruments of data collection are semi-structured interview, field notes and archived training documents. A sample of 15 undergraduate degree holders over 21 years old, who have been self-employed in different industries and possessed entrepreneurial knowledge and experiences were selected using purposive sampling technique. Data from the study were analyzed using coding of the collected data, categorizing the coded data and generating themes in line with the research questions. The study found that pathways to entrepreneurship training towards addressing youth unemployment in Nigeria involves sourcing information/knowledge from different sources that are congruent to entrepreneurial pursuit.

Ezenwakwelu, Egbosiomu and Okwo (2019) examined the effects of apprenticeship training on entrepreneurship development in Nigeria. The study was done using survey research design. Interview was the instrument used for data collection; which was validated by experts from academia and industries. Data collected from the field work were presented using percentages, tables and ratios. The hypotheses formulated in the study were tested using Chi-square with the help of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS v. 20). The study found that apprentices acquire technical and entrepreneurial skills for self employment through formal and informal apprenticeship training systems. The study also revealed that insufficient training tools, inadequate infrastructural facilities, lack of start-up capital and qualified manpower impede apprenticeship system in Nigeria. The study recommended that to boost

entrepreneurship development, the government should provide necessary infrastructure and moral support to aid apprenticeship scheme in Nigeria.

Enimola, Orugun and Nafiu (2019) investigated the effects of entrepreneurial skills on youth employment in Kogi State, with particular emphases on N-Power beneficiaries. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design with questionnaire as research instrument for collecting data from N-Power beneficiaries in N-Tech, N-Health, N-Tax and N-Agro. Descriptive statistics were used for data presentation and analyses, while the hypotheses formulated were tested using Multiple Regression and Ordered Probit Regression Model. The study found that entrepreneurial skills (inter-personal relation skills, technology adoption skills, risk taking skills & decision making skills) have positive significant relationship with youth self-employment in Kogi state. The study concluded that acquisition of entrepreneurial skills is vital for self employment.

Amadi and Opara (2018) examined the impact of entrepreneurship education on acquisition of business skills in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Exploratory survey research design was adopted in the study. The instrument of data collection was structured questionnaire. The population of the study was 236 which were students from 4 tertiary institutions in Rivers state. Using Taro Yamane technique, a sample size of 163 was derived. Data retrieved from the field work were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and hypotheses formulated tested using inferential statistics (ChiSquare). The study found that there is a significant relationship between entrepreneurship education and business skills, measured as: business planning skills, vocational skills and financing skills). The study concluded that entrepreneurship education improves students' business planning skills in tertiary institutions in Nigeria because it exposes students to a lot of business ideas which is useful in planning their dream.

ITF (2014) appraised skills acquisition centers in Nigeria. A cross sectional survey research design was employed in the study. The population of the study includes trainees (1740), instructors (1785) and coordinators/directors of the ITF headquarter, Jos. A multi-stage cluster sampling technique was utilized in the study which resulted to sample size of 3978. Three categories of questionnaire were instruments used in data collection (QASACNC, QASACN & QASACN) which represents questionnaires' used on different respondents: coordinators, instructors and trainees. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics; tables, graphs, means and percentages. The major findings of the study was that ITF training needs were achieved and training programmes improved participants' performance levels on their jobs. The study concluded that programmes offered by skills acquisition centers in Nigeria are making positive impact even though there is still room for improvement.

Hattab (2014) investigated the impact of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of University students in Egypt. The study utilized descriptive survey research design.

Questionnaire was the instrument of data collection and was tested for reliability and internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha to exclude inappropriate items. The population of the study consists of undergraduate students at British University in Egypt from 3 faculties: Engineering, Business Studies (BS) and Computer Studies (CS); totaling 376 students. Questionnaire was distributed to all the students, but only 180 copies were returned, completed and fit for the study. Data collected from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The hypotheses formulated were tested using t-test and f-test

statistics. The study revealed that there is positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and intention; and perceived desirability, while no relationship existed with perceived feasibility or self-efficacy. The study concluded that the educational system in Egypt needs to be reformed to encourage creativity and innovativeness of students.

Ekpe (2017) explored the relationship between skills acquisition, self motivation, social influence and self employment among Malaysian University graduates. Survey research design was utilized in the study. Questionnaire was the instrument of data collection. The population of the study was 600 degree graduates from faculty of Business and Entrepreneurship in Malaysian public Universities and graduated from year 2009 upwards. Stratified random sampling techniques were used to select the sample of 240 students used for the study. 221 copies of the questionnaire were returned, though only 121 copies were used for the analyses. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and hypotheses formulated were tested using correlation method. Findings of the study indicated that self motivation, social influence and skill acquisition have a positive significant influence on self employment amongst Malaysian Business and Entrepreneurship graduates. The study concluded that when necessary authorities and policy makers in Malaysia place emphases on ability to create value to the society; creativity and analytical thinking among those youths will be enhanced.

Mbanefo and Eboka (2019) assessed innovative and entrepreneurial skills needed in basic science education for job creation and teaching strategies required in Nigeria school system. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Questionnaire was the instrument of data collection. Population of the study includes 1441 principals of Junior Secondary Schools and 4340 science teachers in Delta state. Using simple random techniques, 44 principals and 440 science teachers were selected for the study. The questionnaire used in the study was validated by 2 experts and pilot tested to obtain the reliability coefficient using Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.85. Descriptive statistics was used in data analyses and the formulated hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics. The study found that a lot of skills were needed in science education for job creation and practically oriented methods of teaching and delivery were needed to ensure that trainees get the right skills expected of them. The study thus concluded that basic science curriculum needs to be enlarged to have more entrepreneurial experience and teachers need more innovative and entrepreneurial skills for delivery to students.

Ekpe, Razak, Ismail and Abudullah (2015) examined the moderating effect of self-motivation on the relationship between entrepreneurial skills acquisition and self-employment amongst graduates of public Universities in Malaysia. The study employed cross-sectional survey research design. Questionnaire was the instrument of data collection. The population of the study was three Universities from 3 zones of Malaysia peninsular. The sample for the study was selected using simple random sampling techniques. Data retrieved from the field work were analyzed using descriptive statistics and the hypotheses tested using multiple regression. The study found that there is a positive significant relationship between entrepreneurial skills acquisition and self-employment; and self-motivation as a moderator. The study concluded that appropriate strategies need to be employed (counseling in school and at home) to encourage greater participation of youth in self- employment practice.

Agholor (2019) investigated the entrepreneurial skills needed for self-employment by office technology and management graduates of Polytechnics in Nigeria; using Delta state as a case study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study was all the office technology and management lecturers in polytechnics in Delta state, Nigeria. A structured questionnaire was the instrument used in data collection, validated by experts in entrepreneurship and office technology management. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha (α) reliability test coefficient of 0.76. Data collected from the study were analyzed using mean and standard deviation and the hypotheses tested using t- test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that entrepreneurial skills in terms of information and communication technology skills, managerial skills and communication skills are highly needed by graduates of office technology and management programme for self-employment. The study concluded that relevant authorities should ensure that entrepreneurship training infrastructure be deployed fully in department of O.T.M. for quality entrepreneurial skills acquisition.

Eze, Ezenwafor and Igberaharha (2016) assessed the entrepreneurial skills needed for self-employment by graduates of business education in Delta state. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 377. The instrument of data collection was questionnaire, with reliability test of 80% and the validity was checked through pilot study and checked by two senior academic in the faculty. Data collected from the study were analyzed using mean and standard deviation; while Z test was used to test the hypotheses formulated, tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that business education graduates in Delta state, highly needed accounting, office technology, management skills and marketing skills for selfemployment. The study concluded that Delta state business education graduates need entrepreneurial skills (accounting, office technology management and marketing) for self-employment.

Eze and Ekemezie (2015) evaluated the entrepreneurial skills needed by students of Universities for self reliance and sustainable development in South East, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study was 325 lecturers from faculty of education in the five federal Universities in South East, Nigeria. Using stratified random sampling, a sample size of 98 lecturers was realized. The instrument of data collection was structured questionnaire rated on a four point scale, which was tested for reliability using Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient of 0.79. Data from the study were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses formulated were tested using t-test, at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that entrepreneurial skills needed by students of Universities include innovative, creative, administrative and financial skills. The study recommended incorporation of subjects in the curriculum that will help expose these students to other skill acquisition programmes in addition to entrepreneurial education.

Akpan and Etor (2013) investigated lecturers' perception of the relevance of entrepreneurship education to graduates' self-employment in South South, Nigeria; namely: University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, University of Science and Technology, Rivers State, University of Calabar and University of Uyo. Using simple random sampling technique, 480 academic staff, 280 males and 200 females were selected for the study. Questionnaire was the instrument of data collection, which was subjected to face validity using

scrutiny by experts in educational research and then reliability test using test-retest method and reliability coefficient was found to be 0.72. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics: mean and standard deviation. The study found that lecturers were positive in their perception of the relevance of entrepreneurship education as an empowerment strategy for graduate self-employment. The study recommended that government should fund universities adequately to ensure that a well-equipped entrepreneurship centers are in place for practical work and also provide adequate entrepreneurship teachers.

Afolabi, Kareem, Okubanjo, Ogunbanjo and Aninkan (2017) examined the effect of entrepreneurship education on self-employment initiatives amongst science and technology students of Gateway Polytechnic, Saapade Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria. The study was done using descriptive survey research design. Structured questionnaire was the instrument of data collection. Population of the study was 205 students of the polytechnic in their final year classes. Simple random sampling was used to select the sample for the study, and the sample size was calculated using Taro Yamane formula; which added up to 136. Data from the study were analyzed using tables and simple percentage ranking. The hypotheses formulated were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r^2) statistics and simple linear regression. The study revealed that entrepreneurship education is a good policy and has positive effect on self-employment initiatives through its influence on students' interest in entrepreneurial activities and building their choice of business. The study concluded that entrepreneurship education can engender business start-ups by science and technology students without much or less stress.

Okeke, Onuorah, Nebolisa and Odoreh (2019) examined entrepreneurship as an economic force in the development of rural areas of Anambra State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 1350 registered entrepreneurs in Anambra State; and the sample size was 309 which was derived using Taro Yamane formula. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire, which was put through content and face validity test. Data gathered from the study were analyzed using simple percentages and descriptive statistics. The hypotheses formulated in the study were tested using correlation analyses and multiple regression analyses. The study found that access to finance; unemployment and entrepreneurship orientation had significant influence on rural development, while infrastructural facilities had no significant effect on rural development. The study concluded that entrepreneurship as economic force had a significant influence on rural development in Africa.

Nnebe (2019) investigated entrepreneurship education and skills acquisition of graduates in South- East, Nigeria public universities. The study thus explored the effects of technical innovation, creativity, risk taking, opportunity recognition on skills acquisition of graduates of South- East, Nigeria public Universities. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study was done using primary data sources; with structured questionnaire as instrument of data collection; which was validated using face and content validity methods, and the reliability tested using testretest method and Cronbach Alpha Statistics. Data generated from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics and the hypotheses formulated tested using multiple regression analyses. The study found that all the variables studied (technical innovation, creativity, risk taking, opportunity recognition) have significant positive effect on

skills acquisition of graduates in public Universities in South East, Nigeria. The study recommended that technical innovation should be emphasized as technology is imperative in entrepreneurship development. Odewale, Hani, Migiro and Adeyeye (2019) assessed the influence of entrepreneurship education on students view on self-employment. A survey research design was adopted in the study with questionnaire as research instrument. The population of the study consists of active postgraduate students in UUM, which at the time of collecting the data was 741. Using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) technique, a sample size of 254 was arrived at. 260 copies of questionnaires were sent out and 160 were returned and fit for the study. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and the hypotheses tested using linear regression technique; with the help of Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS). The study found that entrepreneurship education (technical knowledge and innovation) influences students' view on self-employment; while communication skills had insignificant relationship on self-employment. The study recommended that educators and policy makers should prioritize technical knowledge and innovation to ensure growth in nascent entrepreneurs.

Okafor (2019) explored entrepreneurship development as a means of reducing unemployment in Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study, with questionnaire as research instrument. The questionnaire was designed using five (5) point modified Likert scale for eliciting information from the respondents who were predominantly practicing entrepreneurs. Data collected from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while Chi-square (χ^2) inferential statistics was used to verify the claims of null hypotheses. The study found that tertiary institutions and other entrepreneurial training centers can be improved to ensure that the training needs are met; and also cost of doing business in Nigeria was found to effect entrepreneurship development negatively. The study concluded that reformation and equipping relevant institutions and training centers will ensure attainment of training needs for acquiring necessary skills and knowledge needed for enterprise creation and its successful management.

Wordu, Igrubia and Okotubu (2018) explored vocational skills acquisition for entrepreneurial skills acquisition for entrepreneurship development and technological advancement in industrial technology education as a strategic approach to surmount economic recession in Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study with questionnaire as research instrument which was tested for validity and a reliability of 0.91 was found; and adequate for the study. Population of the study was 1904 students in tertiary institutions in Rivers state offering TVET programmes. The study adopted systemic sampling technique, with which 225 respondents were selected; comprising 200 students and 25 lecturers. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics and the hypothesis formulated was tested using t-test statistical tools, conducted at 5% level of significance. The study found that skill acquisition in industrial technology education includes proficiency in practical skills and knowledge of vocational and technical studies. The study concluded that a blend of resourceful and productive personnel with adequate industrial technology education would enhance entrepreneurship development and vocational skills acquisition in Nigeria.

Oyefesobi, Adetunji and Ayedun (2018) investigated entrepreneurial skills acquisition and employment generation of Polytechnic graduates of South- West, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Questionnaire was the instrument used in data collection. The population of the study was 3918 Corp Members in Batch B Stream 2, 2017; and a sample size of 647 was selected from all the graduates of public Polytechnic in South West, Nigeria. Cronbach alpha reliability test was used to ensure reliability of the research instrument, which was found a reliability of 0.804, seen adequate for the study. Data collected from the study were analyzed using inferential statistics and the hypotheses formulated were tested using Multiple Regression inferential statistics. The study found that the state of higher education in entrepreneurship is not significant as to ensure employment generation in Nigeria. The study thus concluded that entrepreneurship skills acquisition can lead to self- employment if strategically positioned.

Olokundun (2017) investigated perceptions of students on entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions in selected Nigerian Universities. The study adopted a survey research design and questionnaire was the instrument used in data collection. Semi- structured interview and structured questionnaire were the instruments used for data collection. The reliability of the questionnaire used in the study was tested using pilot study and Cronbach Alpha Coefficient, which was found consistent; at a coefficient of 0.856. The validity of the instrument was also tested by giving the instruments to senior academics in the faculty and their views imputed into the final draft of the instruments. Data collected from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics: frequency, tables, mean and percentages; and the hypotheses formulated were tested using Hierarchical Multiple Regression techniques, with the help of IBM SPSS, version 21. The study found that practicals done in the institutions are based on vocational skills acquisition; and support systems given by the Universities do not reach all the students. The study recommended inclusion of extensive coverage of critical thinking and idea generation activities as graded components of the University programmes.

Omuvwie (2013) investigated performance of Nigeria tertiary institutions business education programme on entrepreneurship. The study adopted a descriptive research design. A self administered questionnaire tagged Students Entrepreneurship Intention Survey Questionnaire (SEISQ) was the instrument used in the study. Test-retest method was used to ensure reliability of the instrument and confirmed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation, which showed a co- efficient of 0.79. The study used a total of 1080 students from the four Universities selected for the study. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics and hypotheses formulated were tested using approximation interpreted as: Very Low (0- 20); Low (21- 40); Moderate (41- 60); High (61- 80) & Very High (81- 100). The study found that there was insignificant change in students' entrepreneurship during the students four years in the University. Also the study found insignificant difference between intentions of business education students and those in other departments. The study concluded that business education has not impacted positively on self-employment initiative and innovation of graduates of Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Ibrahim, Bakar, Asimiran, Mohamed and Zakaria (2015) assessed entrepreneurial intentions level of students in technical and vocational education and training (TVET) institutions in Malaysia. A descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. Questionnaire was the instrument of the study.

Population of the study consists of 513 students in their final semester of Electrical Technology Certificate courses at two technical and vocational education and training institutions in Malaysia. The study used random cluster sampling to select 235 students from the population. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics: means, frequencies and percentages; the formulated hypotheses were tested using t-test. The study found that there is insignificant difference in student entrepreneurship intentions between NYSI students and community college students. The study concluded that both group of students studied do not differ in their entrepreneurial intentions.

Hassan (2013) investigated strategies for curbing unemployment problem in Nigeria through entrepreneurial development. A descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. Questionnaire and oral interview were the instruments of data collection. The population of the study was the entire population of Kogi State. Using Yamani (1962) formula, a sample size of 274 was arrived at and in the choice of sample for the study, simple random sampling was used. Data from the study were analyzed using tables, frequencies and percentages. The formulated hypotheses were tested using Chi-square statistics. The study found that entrepreneurial development programmes of government have not lessened the unemployment situation in Nigeria. Nevertheless, the study concluded that unemployment problem in Nigeria can be solved through entrepreneurial development and that government effort in curbing unemployment in Nigeria is insufficient, hence there is need for more concerted effort in entrepreneurial development.

Otekhile and Mathew (2013) studied innovation and entrepreneurship as catalyst for reduction of youth unemployment in Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Questionnaire was the research instrument used in the study. Data for the study were generated through primary sources, which was administered to self-employed youth that have private businesses in Ota; a small town in Ogun State. The study sample was arrived at using purposive sampling technique. Data gathered from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics; and the formulated hypotheses were analyzed using multiple regression analyses. The study established that there is significant relationship between innovation and entrepreneurship; and youth unemployment. The study concluded that youth need to be empowered by the relevant government authorities and agencies through innovation, creativity and entrepreneurship so as to contribute to eradication of unemployment.

Riti and Kamah (2015) investigated the relationship between entrepreneurship, employment and sustainable development in Nigeria. The study employed ex-post factor research design. Data for the study were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), World Bank Indicators (WBI) and CIA fact sheet; and other extant publications. The study spanned from 1980- 2013. The study adopted co-integration and vector error correction method (VECM); which helped to provide short and long-term estimates of the parameters. The study found that employment and average capacity utilization are statistically significant in the long-run. The study concluded that employment and capacity utilization can be achieved through sustainable entrepreneurship and development; hence a paradigm shift in policy critical to entrepreneurship development is imperative.

Hindu and Onyeukwu (2019) assessed entrepreneurship as a strategic tool for ensuring sustainable development in Nigeria. A survey research design was employed in the study with qualitative and quantitative data gathered using questionnaire and interview method. Out of 150 registered entrepreneurs in Abuja about 50 were selected using convenient sampling method. A self-developed questionnaire tagged entrepreneurship, development, creativity and innovation questionnaire (EDCI) was the instrument of data collection. Ordinary least square regression was the method of estimation used in the study. The study found that entrepreneurship is an indispensable factor for achieving sustainable development; and creativity and innovation predict each other. The study concluded that innovation and creativity drives entrepreneurship, which ensures sustainable development and reduces the challenges of unemployment if adopted effectively in Nigeria.

Imafidon (2014) explored entrepreneurship development as a veritable option for sustaining economic growth in third world nations; using Nigeria as a case study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. Questionnaire was the research instrument used in the study. Using random sampling techniques, 80 entrepreneurs were selected from Edo North, Edo Central and Edo South senatorial district of Edo state in Nigeria. Data collected from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and the hypotheses formulated were tested using Chi-square technique. The study found that entrepreneurship contributes significantly to employment generation and stimulates growth in the economy. The study concluded that entrepreneurship development ensures creation of jobs for Nigerian youth and also stimulates growth.

Zwan, Zuurhout and Hassels (2013) investigated the effect of entrepreneurship education on self employment; and the perceived barriers in the relationship. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. Data for the study were sourced from an international dataset- the Flash Eurobarometer survey on entrepreneurship no. 283. The dataset revealed information on entrepreneurial perceptions and behavior for more than 20,000 individuals in 36 countries in 1900. Data for the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics and relationships amongst the variables were tested using Multinomial Logic Regression. The study found that all the indicators of entrepreneurial learning are positively related with being self-employed. The study also found little evidence that there is relationship between the indicators of entrepreneurial learning and probability of being self-employed is mediated by any of the three perceptions towards entrepreneurship. The study concluded that self-employment decisions can be affected by fostering entrepreneurial skills knowledge, attitude and interest through education and training. Efe-Imafidon, Ade-Adeniji, Umukoro and Ajitemisan (2017) investigated entrepreneurial skills acquisition as a facilitator of self-employability among Nigerian Youths. In the study the researcher examined strategic industries necessary for developing innovative skills by youth, to stimulate self-employment, create jobs and engender economic growth and development in Nigeria. The design used in the study was essentially theoretical, thematic and conceptual. Secondary sources were used in data collection, especially from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) website; where information on strategic industries in Nigeria were identified and assessed; and their contributions to National development. The study found that the strategic industries necessary for youth to acquire necessary skills in order to facilitate employability are; agriculture, industries and services, which are itemized in the study. The study

concluded that every Nigeria youth has option of being self- employed, with necessary assistance by government and nongovernmental agencies.

Gamede and Uleanya (2018) explored entrepreneurship and unemployment in rural communities in South Africa. A qualitative research design was adopted in the study. A semi-structured interview was the instrument of data collection. The population of the study consists of 12 purposively selected final year undergraduate University students from 4 faculties in selected rural based Universities in South Africa. The data retrieved from the interview were coded and thematically analyzed. The study found that absence of infrastructure, supporting policies of the institution and government, wrong orientation given to students, unsupportive University curriculum, socio-economic background of students and students' family belief systems; and lack of corroboration between the University and external bodies; are factors that contributed to lack of entrepreneurial growth in the selected rural communities in South Africa. The study concluded that entrepreneurship is a vital tool for driving sustainable development in any society and entrepreneurial units of the Universities are instrumental to achieving this vision.

Muhammad (2018) investigated the impact of entrepreneurial skills acquisition on home economics students in junior secondary schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria. A single group quasi- experimental research design was adopted in the study. Data for the study were obtained using the instrument tagged: Home Economics Entrepreneurial Skills Performance Test (HEESPT) which was pilot tested and reliability coefficient of 0.83 obtained. Population of the study was 14,830 students studying home economics in junior secondary schools in Kaduna and Rigachikun education zones. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 2 schools from the 2 zones, making a sample size of 90 students. Data collected from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The hypotheses formulated were tested using ANOVA and independent sample t-test statistics. The study found that entrepreneurial skills acquisition has positive influence on performance of Junior Secondary School home economics students in Kaduna State. The study thus concluded that entrepreneurial skills acquisition is important in the schools sampled as it ensures better performance of the students.

Udo (2016) assessed entrepreneurial skills and employment generation among business education graduates in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study adopted a theoretical and conceptual research design. Data from the study were sourced from extant literature; journals, books and other academic materials. The study did in-debth analyses on concepts like entrepreneurship, acquisition of creativity skills, employment generation and generation of resourceful skills. The study found that acquisition of entrepreneurial skills in business education ensures self-sustainability, employment generation, income generation, wealth creation, formation of positive business attitude and crime reduction. The study concluded that entrepreneurship skills when inculcated in business education graduates in Akwa Ibom State will ensure improvement in employment and reduction of social vices in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Adewale, Hani, Migiro and Adeyeye (2019) explored the influence of entrepreneurship education on students view on self-employment in Malaysia. Survey research design was adopted in the study, and questionnaire was the instrument used in the study. Following the technique devised by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), the researcher arrived at sample size of 254 from a population of 750. Data from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Three distinct hypotheses were formulated to guide the

investigation; and were tested using regression analyses. The study revealed that entrepreneurship education: technical knowledge and innovation influences students view on self-employment. The study also found an insignificant relationship between communication skills and students' views on self-employment. The study concluded that technical knowledge and innovation encourages nascent entrepreneurship and influences entrepreneurial performance positively.

Edokpolor and Owenbiugie (2017) assessed the important role of technical and vocational education and training skills on job creation and sustainable development of Nigerian economy. The study adopted survey research design, with questionnaire as instrument for data collection. The population of the study was lecturers from 3 universities and four colleges of education in Edo and Delta States. The questionnaire used in the study was checked for validity and reliability and found suitable for the study. Data from the study were analyzed using mean, standard deviations; and t-test statistics were used to test the hypotheses formulated. The study found that technical, vocational education and training can equip students with skills for job creation and sustainable development in Nigeria. The study concluded that problem of unemployment and underemployment in Nigeria can be ameliorated through effective management of technical and vocational education and training programme.

Georgescu and Herman (2020) investigated the impact of family background on students' entrepreneurial intentions in Romania. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The population of the study comprises selected Romanian high school and University students in their final year; which totals six hundred and seventeen (617). The instrument used in the study was questionnaire, which was distributed non-randomly to the respondents of the selected institutions. Data collected from the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics and the hypotheses formulated were tested using correlation; and a hierarchical analysis of multiple regression. The study found that entrepreneurial family background of students influences their entrepreneurial intentions. Also from the study, other variables that influence entrepreneurial intentions of students are effectiveness of entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial personality traits. More so, entrepreneurial family background negatively moderates the relationship between entrepreneurial intention and effectiveness of entrepreneurship education. The study concluded that young people will choose entrepreneurial career where emphasis is placed on both formal and informal entrepreneurial education.

CONCLUSION

Literature on entrepreneurial skills acquisition and self-employment abound, although various factors mediate in the relationship resulting to a paradox. The literature surveyed expressly points at two most important mediators: self-motivation and social influence. Nevertheless other mediating variables in the said relationship include; entrepreneurship infrastructure, gender and parentage (trait). The reviewed literature is of the view that entrepreneurship skills acquisition influences enterprise creation (Enimola et al. 2019; Oyefesobi et al 2018; Igbogidi, 2017; Onuma, 2016; Muogbo & John- Akamelu, 2018; Ekpe, et al. 2015, 2016; Udo, Ekpe and Razak, 2016; Afolabi et al. 2017; Hattab, 2014; Adetoyi et al., 2014; Akpan and Etor, 2013 Amongst these studies, none looked at the influence of psycho-social factors on relationship between entrepreneurial skills acquisition and enterprise creation in Nigeria. Udida et al. (2012) concluded that self- motivation aid or hinder skills acquisition from leading to youths' self- employment.

In a related study, Ekpe (2017) observed that people from developing countries perceive self-employment as debasing. This poor perception can be noticed from social networks: friends, family, advisors, and role models (Amaikwu, 2011). Psycho-social factors can thus hinder skills acquisition from maturing into self-employment (Ekpe, 2017; Agogbua et al. 2022). The study thus recommends skills acquisition training mix that incorporates relevant environmental variables that inhibits skills acquisition training from resulting to self-employment.

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